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Efficient direct REcycling for low-valUe LFP battery for circular and Sustainable
waste management

D5.1 Visual identity (project website and social network accounts)

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

GA	Grant agreement
RP	Report
D	Deliverable
T	Task
WP	Work Package
WP	Work Package
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

Executive summary

The deliverable D5.1 Visual identity (project website and social network accounts) is a public document of the ReUse project, delivered in the context of WP5 Dissemination and Communication, Task 5.1 Communication & Dissemination activities. This document presents an important step in the objective of developing and deploying the ReUse project website and its identity, dedicated to a wide public audience all around the world.

As a first step, the logo of the project, the visual identity, was developed, and the project website was constructed utilizing the visual identity. The website is available online and can be accessed at www.reuse-batteries.eu. The website is not intended to be static. Especially the “News” and “Resources” sections will be updated regularly and managed by the Dissemination leader – Fenix (FEN) - based on the partner's inputs and project development.

The D5.1 Visual identity (project website and social network accounts) describes the initial design of the website and the visual identity. A relevant part of the dissemination activities foreseen in the project depends on the production of high-quality dissemination materials, based on the project results and activities which are then communicated to target audiences.

1. Project website

The ReUse project website was created and launched during the early stage of the project under the domain www.reuse-batteries.eu. The webhosting and domain were purchased by FEN. Google Analytics is used as a tool to monitor Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and was implemented at an early stage of the project (e.g., views, users, countries, languages, browsers, devices etc.) (Figure 1). Another KPI that will be tracked is the number of downloads from the project website (e.g., promo materials, newsletters). The website was designed to be displayed on various devices such as desktops, mobile or tablets.

FIGURE 1 REUSE WEBSITE ANALYTICS 25/03/2024

2. Website description

The website has been designed by FEN with the main aim to address key questions that external visitors to the website are expected to have, including:

- What is the project about?
- Who is participating in the project?
- What additional details are available?
- Who to contact for more information?
- What other organizations or partnerships ReUse working with (e.g., Battery 2030+, BUILD UP, ECTP)

The website itself contains the following information:

- general information about the project
- partners details
- list of news
- all public material generated by the project
- links to social network profiles
- cooperation information
- newsletter subscription

2.1 Home

The “Home” page of the ReUse website contains basic information about the project. The upper part of the screen displays the project’s logo, links to social profiles and a navigation panel. At the top of the page there is the project’s title, a brief project overview (incl. objective, funding, and team) and links to other pages that provide more information. Next on the “Home” page is the project’s introduction, a subscription option to the newsletter, contact information, and an overview of latest project news. The footer of all pages includes options to subscribe to the newsletter, information about funding, links to social media and the privacy policy (as shown in Figure 2).

2.2 About

The “About” page includes further information about the project’s mission and consortium. It provides a brief description of the project coordinator, as well as contact details. Each partner’s name, logo and a link to the partner’s website are displayed as shown in Figure 2. This part of the website will remain static, unless there is a partner change, or a logo change in the project.

FIGURE 2 HOME AND ABOUT PAGES

2.3 News

The “News” page contains a list of news and events, which will cover all meetings of the project partners, project updates, publications, and important events such as conferences, fairs, and workshops (Figure 3). A brief summary of the latest news is also displayed on the “Home” page as shown in Figure 2.

2.4 Resources

The “Resources” section in the menu navigation will be divided into three pages: Documents, Gallery and Videos. The Documents page will include promotional materials and publications, public deliverables, press releases and newsletters. Subsections can be added based on the project’s requirements and progress at any time. The Documents page will contain all published materials that are open access (respecting copyright issues) as shown in Figure 3.

2.5 Link to the Battery2030+ initiative

The “Battery2030” page offers comprehensive insights about the European research initiative that plays a crucial role in the European battery “ecosystem” by inventing the sustainable batteries of the future (Ref. battery.eu/research/roadmap). Tailored for key stakeholders in battery research, this page provides access to the initiative's website and features essential resources such as the Battery2030+ Roadmap and contact details for the Director of Battery2030+ (as shown in Figure 3)

FIGURE 3 NEWS, RESOURCES AND BATTERY2030 PAGES

2.6 Cookies

Cookies are small text files stored on a user's computer by their browser. They have many applications, such as: tracking users on a website, remembering user preferences, enabling auto-logins for returning visitors, and enhancing website security. The ReUse project website has also implemented a cookies policy to help the site provide a better user experience. In general, cookies are used to retain user preferences, store information, and provide tracking data to third-party applications like Google Analytics.

2.7 Future work

Short-term improvements being considered for the website at the time of writing this deliverable include:

- updating the website content to reflect the project's progress
- updating the information on the About page
- creating a gallery and video page.

3. Project visual identity

The objectives of the project identity are:

- to develop a design structure that can accommodate standard project identity elements, provide an adaptable visual identity for various uses, and effectively convey thematic information when necessary;
- to allow immediate recognition of the ReUse project through standardized communication templates designed for external audiences;
- to develop specific guidelines and structures related to the project, such as a defined set of colours and/or typography.

These guidelines should be applied to templates that are easy to adapt, understand and use by the project partners.

3.1 Project logo

The initial task for the dissemination of material design is logo development. The logo was recreated by FEN in vector format at the beginning of the project to establish a distinct project identity (see Figure 4 and 5). The logo was designed to be simple and easily recognizable. During the logo design process, it was important to ensure that it aligns with current branding trends, so that the design remains up to date throughout the whole project lifecycle. The target audience must identify the logo at first glance; therefore, the logo should be easy to remember and reflect the project's objectives.

FIGURE 4 REUSE LOGO

FIGURE 5 LOGO COLOUR VARIATION

The project logo can be used in the following cases:

- in all documents developed within the ReUse project, including those to be submitted to the EC (e.g., deliverables)
- in PowerPoint presentations used for communication and dissemination activities to be carried out by each participant in the framework of the project, as well as in all promotion materials
- on the ReUse website, and on the websites of the participants` with a link to the project website

3.2 Brand manual

It is important to adhere to and respect the project's visual identity in order to maximize the impact on the audience. For this reason, a brand manual has been created, outlining the graphical identity guidelines (colour palette, logo variants and typography) (Figure 6). The logos and brand manual can be downloaded from the project website (<https://www.reuse-batteries.eu/resources>).

FIGURE 6 BRAND MANUAL

3.3 Funding

According to the ReUse Grant Agreement and Article 17.2 “Visibility – European flag and funding statement”, unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, beneficiaries of the project must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement in their communication activities related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major results funded by the grant (as shown below in Figure 7).

Additionally, due to the Swiss contribution to the funding, additional acknowledgement is required and shown below in Figure 8.

FIGURE 7 EU EMBLEM

FIGURE 8 SWISS ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

3.4 Dissemination material

In the initial stage of the project, dissemination materials will be designed to support the communication and dissemination activities of the ReUse project, as part of Task 5.1 - Communication & Dissemination activities. These dissemination materials will be regularly updated to align with the project’s progress. All dissemination material is currently available on the project website (www.reuse-batteries.eu) and will continue to be accessible there.

3.5 Future work

Short-term work being considered at the time of writing this deliverable includes:

- updating the website content, pages and sections to reflect the project's progress
- creating a project presentation
- designing flyers and roll-ups
- creating an introduction video by M6.

4. Social media

During the start of the project, a LinkedIn profile page was created to maximize the visibility of published results and the participation of project partners in international events, as well as to gather feedback from stakeholders (see Figure 9). Additionally, a YouTube channel was established as a platform for sharing both long and short-format videos.

The links to these social media platforms have been added to the project website and will be included in all future newsletters. FEN manages and updates the profiles based on the partners' contributions (general information about the project, updates about the project progress, dissemination activities, infographics, and news from the related field).

FIGURE 9 REUSE LINKEDIN PROFILE

5. Conclusion

The online ReUse website plays a crucial role in the project's dissemination and communication strategy. It serves to increase the visibility of the project, facilitate the distribution of the results, and promote their exploitation. The ReUse project website has been designed, provisioned, and deployed on the internet. Currently consisting mostly of static content, it has been designed to answer the key questions anticipated from external website visitors. As the project progresses, the project website will continue to evolve and develop.

The information available on the website is expected to remain valuable even after the project has finished. Therefore, the consortium aims to ensure the website's continuity beyond the 3-year funding period, ensuring that bookmarks and published URLs will remain functional to support the project's impact.

All dissemination materials generated will adhere to the ReUse project's visual identity guidelines, which have been designed to follow the project's progress. All open access materials will be made available to the public on the project website and used during dissemination events. More detailed information will be provided in the D5.2 -Dissemination and Communication Plan.